

Deliverable D4.3

UNITA report on Open Data and shared research infrastructures and services

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Abstract

Context and Objectives: Task 4.3 of the UNITA initiative aims to consolidate and implement a comprehensive plan for sharing infrastructures and related services among partner universities, ensuring broad access for a wide range of users. The research infrastructures considered include laboratory facilities, computational resources, and other scientific services. An Open Data policy will be adopted, in alignment with the 2016 European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures and its associated principles and guidelines.

Methodology: A roadmap has been developed with four main activities to establish a tested *modus operandi* for infrastructure sharing within the UNITA alliance. These activities include a) redesigning and developing the database of shared infrastructures built during the RE-UNITA project (101035810 – Re-UNITA – H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-2-2020) to adapt it for the UNITA 2 project, b) revising and improving the internal regulations and methodologies for sharing infrastructures, c) piloting and testing the functionalities of the redesigned system, and d) elaborating the final version of the *modus operandi*.

Results and Outcomes: The shared infrastructure database has been expanded and upgraded to accommodate the UNITA 2 consortium. Notable updates include the addition of new universities, each with a unique login, and the introduction of a "hub" tab allowing up to focus on the six research thematic hubs of our alliance. A management delegation model has been established where each partner designates a responsible person for maintaining their respective sections of the database. The first phase requires all equipment to be listed by January 2025, with continuous updates throughout the project. The infrastructure sharing agreement has been adapted for the UNITA alliance, and it was signed by the rectors of the partner universities during the governance board meeting held at UNIBS Brescia on October 29, 2024. Although HES-SO opted not to sign at this stage, it will be included later, facilitated by an endorsement.

Impact and Applications: The shared infrastructure database is now accessible to all researchers within the UNITA alliance, enabling the exchange of equipment, measurements, and analyses and more than 250 equipment, services are proposed. The application form for the first call for projects is under development, which will further support researchers in utilizing the shared resources in the database. Strong links with the research thematic HUBs are being cultivated to enhance collaboration and access.

Conclusions and Next Steps: Discussions are underway to determine which infrastructures universities and institutes are willing to share. Special attention is being given to prioritizing unique, high-value instruments that benefit the UNITA 2 scientific community, rather than duplicating commonly available instruments. The first infrastructure-sharing call is scheduled for March 2025, with ongoing work focused on refining the application process and setting clear criteria for participation.

Keywords

Shared Equipment, Database, UNITA Infrastructure network, Research

FR

Contexte et objectifs : La tâche 4.3 UNITA a pour objectifs de consolider et mettre en œuvre le partage d'infrastructures et de services dédiés au sein des universités partenaires, afin d'assurer un large accès à ces services pour nos communautés. Par infrastructures de recherche, nous intégrons les équipements de laboratoires, les ressources techniques et l'ensemble des services et plateforme scientifiques. Une politique de données ouvertes sera implémentée, alignée avec la Charte européenne pour l'accès aux infrastructures de recherche.

Méthodologie : Une feuille de route a été élaborée avec quatre activités principales pour établir un *modus operandi* testé pour le partage des infrastructures au sein de l'alliance UNITA. Ces activités comprennent a) le remaniement et le développement de la base de données des infrastructures partagées construite pendant le projet RE-UNITA pour l'adapter au projet UNITA, b) la révision et l'amélioration des règlements internes et des méthodologies pour le partage des infrastructures, c) le pilotage et le test des fonctionnalités du système remanié, et d) l'élaboration de la version finale du *modus operandi*.

Résultats et réalisations : La base de données des infrastructures partagées a été étendue et mise à jour pour s'adapter au nouveau consortium UNITA. Parmi les mises à jour notables, on peut citer l'ajout de nouvelles universités, chacune disposant d'un identifiant unique, et l'introduction d'un champ « hub » permettant d'associer une infrastructure jusqu'à trois hubs différents. Un modèle de délégation de gestion a été mis en place, dans lequel chaque partenaire désigne une personne responsable de la maintenance de ses sections respectives de la base de données. La première phase exige que tous les équipements soient répertoriés d'ici janvier 2025, avec des mises à jour continues tout au long du projet. L'accord de partage d'infrastructure a été adapté à l'alliance UNITA et a été signé par les recteurs des universités partenaires lors de la réunion du conseil de gouvernance le 29 octobre 2024. Bien que la HES-SO ait choisi de ne pas signer à ce stade, elle sera incluse ultérieurement, ce qui sera facilité par un avenant.

Impact et mise en œuvre : La base de données des infrastructures partagées est désormais accessible à tous les chercheurs et techniciens de l'alliance UNITA, ce qui permet l'échange d'équipements, de mesures et d'analyses, et plus de 250 équipements et services sont proposés. Le formulaire de réponse au premier appel à projets est en cours d'élaboration, ce qui aidera davantage les chercheurs à utiliser les ressources partagées de la base de données. Des liens étroits avec les hubs sont cultivés pour améliorer la collaboration et l'accès.

Conclusions et prochaines étapes : Des discussions sont en cours pour déterminer quelles infrastructures les universités et les instituts sont prêts à partager. Une attention particulière est accordée à la priorité donnée aux instruments uniques et de grande valeur qui profitent à la communauté scientifique d'UNITA 2, plutôt qu'à la duplication d'instruments couramment disponibles. Le premier appel à partage d'infrastructures est prévu pour mars 2025, les travaux en cours étant axés sur l'affinement du processus de candidature et l'établissement de critères de participation clairs.

Mots clés : Infrastructures partagées, réseau UNITA, recherche

RO

Context și obiective: Sarcina 4.3 a inițiativei UNITA își propune să consolideze și să implementeze un plan cuprinzător de partajare a infrastructurilor și a serviciilor conexe între universitățile partenere, asigurând un acces larg pentru o gamă largă de utilizatori. Infrastructurile de cercetare luate în considerare includ facilități de laborator, resurse de calcul și alte servicii științifice. Va fi adoptată o politică de date deschise, în conformitate cu Carta europeană pentru acces la infrastructurile de cercetare din 2016 și cu principiile și orientările asociate acesteia.

Metodologie: A fost elaborată o foaie de parcurs cu patru activități principale pentru a stabili un modus operandi testat pentru partajarea infrastructurii în cadrul alianței UNITA. Aceste activități includ a) re-proiectarea și dezvoltarea bazei de date a infrastructurilor partajate construite în timpul proiectului RE-UNITA (101035810 – Re-UNITA – H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-2-2020) pentru a o adapta pentru proiectul UNITA, b) revizuirea și îmbunătățirea reglementărilor interne și a metodologiilor de partajare a infrastructurilor, c) pilotarea și testarea funcționalităților sistemului re-proiectat și d) elaborarea versiunii finale a modus operandi.

Rezultate și rezultate: Baza de date a infrastructurii partajate a fost extinsă și modernizată pentru a găzdui consorțiul UNITA 2. Actualizările notabile includ adăugarea de noi universități, fiecare cu o autentificare unică, și introducerea unei file „hub” care permite să ne concentrăm asupra celor șase centre tematice de cercetare ale alianței noastre. A fost stabilit un model de delegare a managementului în care fiecare partener desemnează o persoană responsabilă pentru întreținerea secțiunilor respective ale bazei de date. Prima fază necesită ca toate echipamentele să fie listate până în ianuarie 2025, cu actualizări continue pe tot parcursul proiectului. Acordul de partajare a infrastructurii a fost adaptat pentru alianța UNITA și a fost semnat de rectorii universităților partenere în cadrul ședinței consiliului de guvernare desfășurat la UNIBS Brescia pe 29 octombrie 2024. Deși HES-SO a optat să nu semneze în această etapă, acesta va fi inclus ulterior, facilitat de o avizare.

Impact și aplicații: Baza de date a infrastructurii partajate este acum accesibilă tuturor cercetătorilor din cadrul alianței UNITA, permițând schimbul de echipamente, măsurători și analize și sunt propuse peste 250 de echipamente, servicii. Formularul de cerere pentru primul apel de proiecte este în curs de dezvoltare, cu rolul de a sprijini în continuare cercetătorii în utilizarea resurselor partajate din baza de date. Este propusă

dezvoltarea unor legături puternice cu HUB-urile tematice de cercetare pentru a îmbunătăți colaborarea și accesul.

Concluzii și pași următori: Discuțiile sunt în desfășurare pentru a determina care sunt infrastructurile pe care sunt dispuse universitățile și institutele să le împărtășească. Se acordă o atenție deosebită prioritizării echipamentelor/instrumentelor unice, de mare valoare, de care să beneficieze comunitatea științifică UNITA, comparativ cu practicile de dublare a echipamentelor/instrumentelor disponibile în mod obișnuit. Primul apel de partajare a infrastructurii este programat pentru martie 2025, iar lucrările în desfășurare se concentrează pe rafinarea procesului de aplicare și pe stabilirea unor criterii clare de participare.

Cuvinte cheie:

Echipe partajate, baza de date, rețeaua de infrastructură UNITA, cercetare

IT

Contesto e obiettivi: Il task 4.3 dell'iniziativa UNITA mira a consolidare e attuare un piano completo per la condivisione delle infrastrutture e dei relativi servizi tra le università partner, garantendo un ampio accesso a una vasta gamma di utenti. Le infrastrutture di ricerca considerate includono strutture di laboratorio, risorse di calcolo e altri servizi scientifici. Sarà adottata una politica di Open Data, in linea con la Carta europea per l'accesso alle infrastrutture di ricerca del 2016 e con i principi e le linee guida ad essa associati.

Metodologia: È stata sviluppata una tabella di marcia con quattro attività principali per stabilire un modus operandi collaudato per la condivisione delle infrastrutture all'interno dell'alleanza UNITA. Queste attività includono a) la riprogettazione delle infrastrutture di ricerca e dei servizi di ricerca. Queste attività comprendono:

- a) la riprogettazione e lo sviluppo del database delle infrastrutture condivise costruito durante il progetto RE-UNITA (101035810 - Re-UNITA - H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-2-2020) per adattarlo al progetto UNITA;
- b) la revisione e il miglioramento dei regolamenti interni e delle metodologie per la condivisione delle infrastrutture;
- c) il pilotaggio e il test delle funzionalità del sistema riprogettato; d) l'elaborazione della versione finale del modus operandi.

Risultati e esiti: Il database dell'infrastruttura condivisa è stato ampliato e migliorato per accogliere il consorzio UNITA 2. Tra gli aggiornamenti degni di nota figurano l'aggiunta di nuove università, ciascuna con un login unico, e l'introduzione di una scheda "hub" che consente di concentrarsi sui sei hub tematici di ricerca della nostra alleanza. È stato stabilito un modello di delega della gestione in cui ogni partner designa un responsabile per la manutenzione delle rispettive sezioni del database. La prima fase prevede che tutte le attrezzature siano elencate entro gennaio 2025, con aggiornamenti continui nel corso del progetto. L'accordo di condivisione delle infrastrutture è stato adattato all'alleanza UNITA ed è stato firmato dai rettori delle università partner durante la riunione del consiglio di amministrazione tenutasi presso l'UNIBS di Brescia il 29 ottobre 2024. Sebbene HES-SO abbia scelto di non firmare in questa fase, sarà incluso in seguito, facilitato da un endorsement.

Impatto e applicazioni: Il database dell'infrastruttura condivisa è ora accessibile a tutti i ricercatori all'interno dell'alleanza UNITA, consentendo lo scambio di apparecchiature, misure e analisi e sono stati proposti più di 250 attrezzature e servizi. È in fase di sviluppo il modulo di candidatura per il primo invito a presentare progetti, che supporterà ulteriormente i ricercatori nell'utilizzo delle risorse condivise nel database. Si stanno coltivando forti legami con gli HUB di ricerca per migliorare la collaborazione e l'accesso.

Conclusioni e passi successivi: Sono in corso discussioni per determinare quali infrastrutture le università e gli istituti sono disposti a condividere. Si sta prestando particolare attenzione a dare priorità a strumenti unici e di alto valore che siano utili alla comunità scientifica di UNITA, piuttosto che a duplicare strumenti comunemente disponibili. Il primo bando per la condivisione delle infrastrutture è previsto per marzo 2025, mentre il lavoro in corso si concentra sul perfezionamento del processo di candidatura e sulla definizione di criteri chiari per la partecipazione.

Parole chiave

Apparecchiature condivise, Database, Rete infrastrutturale UNITA, Ricerca

ES

Contexto y Objetivos: La Tarea 4.3 de la iniciativa UNITA tiene como objetivo consolidar e implementar un plan integral para compartir infraestructuras y servicios relacionados entre las universidades socias, garantizando un amplio acceso para diversos tipos de usuarios. Las infraestructuras de investigación consideradas incluyen instalaciones de laboratorio, recursos computacionales y otros servicios científicos. Se adoptará una política de Datos Abiertos, en consonancia con la Carta Europea de 2016 para el Acceso a Infraestructuras de Investigación y sus principios y directrices asociadas.

Metodología: Se ha desarrollado una hoja de ruta con cuatro actividades principales para establecer un modus operandi probado para el intercambio de infraestructuras dentro de la alianza UNITA. Estas actividades incluyen:

- a) rediseñar y desarrollar la base de datos de infraestructuras compartidas creada durante el proyecto RE-UNITA (101035810 – Re-UNITA – H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-2-2020) para adaptarla al proyecto UNITA;
- b) revisar y mejorar las normativas internas y metodologías para el intercambio de infraestructuras;
- c) pilotar y probar las funcionalidades del sistema rediseñado;
- d) elaborar la versión final del modus operandi.

Resultados y Logros: Se ha ampliado y mejorado la base de datos de infraestructuras compartidas para su adaptación al consorcio UNITA. Las actualizaciones más reseñables incluyen la incorporación de nuevas universidades, cada una con un inicio de sesión único, y la introducción de una pestaña de "hub" que permite centrarse en los seis centros temáticos de investigación de nuestra alianza. Se ha establecido un modelo de delegación de gestión donde cada socio designa a una persona responsable de mantener sus respectivas secciones de la base de datos. La primera fase requiere que todo el equipo esté registrado para enero de 2025, con actualizaciones continuas a lo largo del proyecto. El acuerdo para compartir infraestructuras adaptado para la alianza UNITA fue firmado por los rectores de las universidades socias en reunión del consejo de gobierno celebrada en UNIBS Brescia el 29 de octubre de 2024. Aunque HES-SO optó por no firmar en esta etapa, se incluirá posteriormente mediante ratificación.

Impacto y Aplicaciones: En la actualidad, la base de datos de infraestructuras compartidas está accesible para todos los investigadores dentro de la alianza UNITA, permitiendo el intercambio de equipos, mediciones y análisis. Más de 250 equipos y servicios están disponibles. Se está desarrollando un formulario de solicitud para la primera convocatoria de proyectos, lo que apoyará aún más a los investigadores en el uso de los recursos compartidos en la base de datos. Se están fortaleciendo los vínculos con los HUBs temáticos de investigación para mejorar la colaboración y el acceso.

Conclusiones y Próximos Pasos: Se están llevando a cabo discusiones para determinar qué infraestructuras están dispuestas a compartir las universidades e institutos. Se presta especial atención a priorizar instrumentos únicos y de alto valor que benefician a la comunidad científica de UNITA, en lugar de duplicar instrumentos de uso común. La primera convocatoria para el intercambio de infraestructuras está programada para marzo de 2025, con trabajo continuo en la mejora del proceso de solicitud y el establecimiento de criterios claros de participación.

Palabras clave: Equipos compartidos, Base de datos, Red de infraestructuras UNITA, Investigación

PT

Contexto e Objetivos: A Tarefa 4.3 da iniciativa UNITA tem como objetivo consolidar e implementar um plano abrangente para o compartilhamento de infraestruturas científicas e serviços relacionados entre as universidades parceiras, garantindo um amplo acesso para uma grande variedade de utilizadores. As infraestruturas de investigação consideradas incluem instalações laboratoriais, recursos computacionais e outros serviços científicos. Será adotada uma política de Dados Abertos, alinhada com a Carta Europeia para o Acesso a Infraestruturas de Investigação de 2016 e os seus princípios e diretrizes associadas.

Metodologia: Foi desenvolvido um roteiro com quatro atividades principais para estabelecer um modelo de operação testado para a partilha de infraestruturas dentro da aliança UNITA. Estas atividades incluem: a) redesenhar e desenvolver a base de dados de infraestruturas partilhadas construída durante o projeto RE-UNITA (101035810 – Re-UNITA – H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-2-2020) para adaptá-la ao projeto UNITA, b) rever

e melhorar os regulamentos internos e metodologias para a partilha de infraestruturas, c) pilotar e testar as funcionalidades do sistema redesenhado, e d) elaborar a versão final do modus operandi.

Resultados e Produtos da tarefa: A base de dados de infraestruturas partilhadas foi expandida e atualizada para acomodar o consórcio UNITA. As atualizações notáveis incluem a adição de novas universidades, cada uma com uma autenticação única, e a introdução de uma aba "hub" que permite focar nos seis centros temáticos de investigação da nossa aliança. Foi estabelecido um modelo de delegação de gestão, onde cada parceiro designa uma pessoa responsável pela manutenção das suas respetivas secções da base de dados. A primeira fase exige que todos os equipamentos sejam listados até janeiro de 2025, com atualizações contínuas ao longo do projeto. O acordo de compartilhamento de infraestruturas foi adaptado para a aliança UNITA e foi assinado pelos reitores das universidades parceiras durante a reunião do conselho de governação realizada na UNIBS Brescia em 29 de outubro de 2024. Embora a HES-SO tenha optado por não assinar nesta fase, será incluída posteriormente, através de patrocínio da iniciativa.

Impacto e Aplicações: A base de dados de infraestruturas partilhadas está agora acessível a todos os investigadores da aliança UNITA, permitindo o intercâmbio de equipamentos, medições e análises e mais de 250 equipamentos e serviços são propostos. O formulário de candidatura para o primeiro concurso de projetos está em desenvolvimento, o que irá apoiar ainda mais os investigadores na utilização dos recursos partilhados na base de dados. Estão a ser cultivados fortes laços com os centros temáticos de investigação para melhorar a colaboração e o acesso.

Conclusões e Próximos Passos: Estão em curso discussões para determinar quais infraestruturas as universidades e os institutos estão dispostos a partilhar. Está a ser dada especial atenção à priorização de instrumentos únicos e de alto valor que beneficiem a comunidade científica UNITA, em vez de duplicar instrumentos disponíveis de forma comum. O primeiro concurso de compartilhamento de infraestruturas está agendado para março de 2025, com trabalhos contínuos focados no aperfeiçoamento do processo de candidatura e na definição de critérios claros para participação.

Palavras-chave: Equipamentos Partilhados, Base de Dados, Rede de Infraestruturas UNITA, Investigação

Table of contents

Description.....	9
Discussion of the final outcome	10
Conclusions	13
Annexes	15

Description

This task aims to consolidate and implement the UNITA plan for sharing partners' infrastructures and related services, ensuring access to a wide range of users. Research infrastructures are considered in a broad sense, encompassing laboratory facilities as well as computing facilities and services. An Open Data policy will be adopted, aligning with the 2016 European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures and its associated principles and guidelines¹.

Task 4.3 is structured into five key actions², as outlined below (annex 1):

- A4.3.1 Finalize and update the mapping of partners' infrastructures and related services initiated by Re-UNITA (101035810 – Re-UNITA – H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-2-2020) (M1-M12). Promote the exchange of best practices for infrastructure management and sharing. Derive key insights to facilitate further development and sharing of infrastructures and associated services.
- A4.3.2 Strengthen the model for sharing research infrastructures and services through decentralized management and Open Data principles (M5-M15). Define preferential fees, fee waivers, and cost-sharing mechanisms within UNITA alliance. Prioritize access to major and complementary infrastructures with significant potential for utilization by all partners, including Associated Partners and the GEMINAE network, while aligning with the alliance's focus areas in education, research, and innovation. Aim to integrate these infrastructures into a European project repository.
- A4.3.3 Launch regular funding calls to co-finance access to infrastructures (M13-M48), enabling researchers to engage in multi-partner projects and address infrastructure gaps. Propose sustainable, long-term solutions leveraging national, private, and EU funding. Create an interactive, user-friendly platform for infrastructure sharing within the UNITA inter-university digital campus, establishing a "scientific marketplace" to facilitate partnerships and provide training on infrastructure usage. Implement and test systemic procedures for sharing services and infrastructures, ensuring mutual access to facilities.
- A4.3.4 Assess necessary system modifications (M13-M36) and develop procedures for implementation at partner institutions, ensuring compliance with legal, technical, and financial requirements. Work towards fostering a cohesive UNITA identity for shared research services and infrastructures.
- A4.3.5 Enhance the system by making necessary improvements and intensifying the sharing of services and infrastructures (M36-M48). Strive to fully integrate research capacities within the shared UNITA corporate identity. Expand the network to incorporate facilities provided by Associated Partners and the GEMINAE network.

A roadmap for the first year (extending to the first 15 months) has been developed. Four main activities were identified and planned to be carried out during this period to establish and test a modus operandi for sharing infrastructures within the UNITA alliance.

1. Redesign and development of the database of shared infrastructures created under the RE-UNITA project (101035810 – Re-UNITA – H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-2-2020) to adapt it for the UNITA 2 project (linked to A4.3.1). Specifically:
 - The historical and founding members of UNITA revised the list of infrastructures they had previously proposed for sharing.
 - The new partners involved in the consolidation phase of UNITA decided on the initial equipment or specific infrastructures they wish to share.
 - The modes of sharing infrastructures were clarified, with several possible scenarios:
 - Infrastructures can be operated or used solely by staff from the host university sharing the infrastructure.

¹ doi:10.2777/524573

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/78e87306-48bc-11e6-9c64-01aa75ed71a1>

² Task 4.3, as proposed and approved in the UNITA 2 program, is structured around a roadmap spanning the duration of the project. This roadmap consists of five main pillars, as outlined in the report above. The official document can be consulted in Annex 1.

- Infrastructures can be operated or used by other alliance partners, accompanied by staff from the host university sharing the infrastructure.
- Infrastructures can be operated or used by other alliance partners, provided they follow internal procedures, which may include training on equipment usage.
- Publication of the database of shared infrastructures with improved features compared to the previous project:
 - The database is designed to be continuously enriched.
 - A broad dissemination within UNITA institutions is planned.

This activity requires extensive dissemination across universities using various channels.

2. Revising and improving the set of internal regulations and methodologies for sharing infrastructures within UNITA (linked to A4.3.2; A4.3.3 and A4.3.4). Specifically:

- Centralizing and analysing the set of specific regulations related to the usage of shared infrastructures in all UNITA institutions
- Discussing the fees of shared infrastructures*

To facilitate the large usage of shared infrastructures, the fees definition is carefully analysed, for at least several reasons:

- Fees must align with the constraints of the institution hosting the infrastructures.
- Fees must be "accessible" to all or most universities.
- Maximizing the volume of shared infrastructures should remain the ultimate goal.
- A concise report on the regulations and methodologies governing the sharing of infrastructures must be prepared.

3. Piloting and testing the functionalities of the redesigned UNITA 2 shared infrastructure database (linked to A4.3.1 and A4.3.3)

- Testing the system, focusing on the number of requests and effective sharing of infrastructures over a 4-month period following the launch of the shared infrastructure database (M18)
- Identifying weaknesses and corrective measures

4. Summative report

- Elaborating the annual report
- Elaborating the final version of Modus operandi (leaflet)

Discussion of the final outcome

The completed actions correspond to the points 1) and 2) of the first year roadmap were described previously. More precisely here are the different activities that were conducted to achieve goals. No deviations from the Description of Action (DoA) were observed.

The Re-designing and development of the database of shared infrastructures was adapted to the extended alliance with its 12 Institutions (UNITA alliance):

- Proposal of a training model: A template has been created to outline the training required for registering new equipment in the shared infrastructure database (see annex 2).
- Database operational management: Discussions were held to determine the best approach for maintaining the database. The University of Zaragoza (UNIZAR) has taken responsibility for creating and managing the database. The chosen solution involves maintaining and developing the database to meet the needs of the new UNITA alliance. Built using the Drupal Content Management System (CMS), the database's structure remains unchanged, though it can be adapted as needed.

- Database enhancements: The database has been expanded and upgraded to accommodate the UNITA 2 consortium and incorporate changes decided during T4.3 meetings³. Specific updates include:
 - New universities that have joined the alliance in UNITA 2 have been added to the database, each one with a unique username and password.
 - A “hub” field has been introduced, allowing to access the database through its 6 Thematic research hubs.
 - Technical staff have been nominated by each partner institution (except HES-SO) to modify the database content, with contact details provided for these representatives.

Homepage of the UNITA 2 Shared Infrastructure Database

³ Link to access the shared infrastructure database site: https://www.research.univ-unita.eu/en/index.html#infrastructure_database

CESAR (Supercomputing Centre)

Kind of infrastructure Singular equipments	
Typology Advanced data / calculation	
University Zaragoza (UNIZAR)	
Hubs Digital transition	
Application / Industrial sector Agrifood Health Mobility & transportation	

Example of a shared infrastructure available in the database

- Database management delegation has been decided: Each partner institution nominates a responsible person for database management. Partners have access to their respective sections of the database to modify and update their records. Each university fills out the mandatory fields for every piece of equipment or service to be shared. Phase 1 requires all equipment to be listed by January 2025, while updates and improvements to the database continue throughout the project.

The infrastructure sharing agreement has been extended to the all UNITA alliance (annex 3). Its purpose is to formalise a simple and general internal methodology for infrastructure sharing within UNITA 2. The sharing agreement is suitable for all alliance partners. It is essential because it commits the partners to sharing equipment and infrastructure as part of the UNITA 2 project. The rectors of the alliance universities signed the agreement during the governance board meeting in Brescia on 29 October 2024 (see picture below). HES-SO decided to postpone its participation to this agreement but will be included later when ready, with an endorsement prepared to facilitate its inclusion.

Unita's Rectors signing the protocol for Shared infrastructures during UNIBS Governance Board. Brescia, 29th of October 2024.

Ongoing key actions can be highlighted:

- A key point is the reflection on the determination of the infrastructures that universities and institutes are willing to share. Particular attention should be paid to avoid sharing instruments that are available in all universities and instead focus on complementary, unique or high-value instruments that benefit the UNITA scientific community. This point addresses both actions 4.3.2 and 4.3.4, which run until months M15 and M36, respectively.
- Call structure discussions: T4.3 team members are working on the definition of the application process for the first infrastructure-sharing call. The application form will be general and adaptable to a wide range of requests, with key criteria clearly outlined. This action is part of the Launch regular funding calls, planned from months M13 to M48. It is expected to start in month M17 as the call is currently under construction.

Some Upcoming key actions are imminent. These actions are not completely identified in the roadmap for the first 15 months of the project but are a logical continuation of the tasks to be carried out as described in the actions of WP4. key actions. They could form the start of the next roadmap.

- Model consolidation for infrastructure sharing: A decentralized management model based on Open Data principles will be finalized. Three sharing modalities have been discussed:
 - Infrastructure is operated solely by the host technical staff, with the guest researcher allowed to assist during analysis.
 - Infrastructure is partially accessible to the guest researchers after a short training session by the host institution
 - Infrastructure can be fully used by guest researchers under the supervision of its manager.

The model will be completed with a review of the nature and quality of the shared equipment and infrastructure very shortly. The aim is twofold: on the one hand, to offer researchers an effective tool to facilitate the deployment of their work through easier access to equipment and infrastructure. Secondly, to create a technical and scientific identity around (among other things) this database by sharing complementary or exceptional equipment within the alliance, making this database a unique tool at the service of high-level research.

- Access fee considerations: A review of access fees for shared infrastructures has been discussed. Following previous activities carried out in the frame of Re-UNITA's WP4, internal rates (the lowest possible fees) should be preferred and applied across UNITA. In addition, some alliance partners have not yet set internal rates. In this case, access to shared infrastructures could be based on the cost of the consumables needed to carry out the experiments.
- Launch of the first call for projects: The final version of the application form will be completed by early 2025, with the first call for co-financing access to infrastructures planned for March 2025
- A concise report on the regulations and methodologies ruling the sharing of infrastructures will be elaborated as a leaflet. It could be both a methodological guide to the best use of the shared infrastructure database and a dissemination document (leaflet/booklet) to promote the use of this facility.

Conclusions

Task 4.3 has completed the actions 1) and 2) outlined in its initial phase (first 15months roadmap). Key milestones include the redesign and enhancement of the shared infrastructure database, which now incorporates additional features to accommodate new members of the UNITA alliance and ensure complete connection with the research thematic HUBs. The definition of a simplified agreement for sharing resources reflects a strong commitment to operational efficiency and fairness among partners. Stakeholder engagement, such as the rectors' signature of the agreement, underscores the institutional support for this collaborative effort.

Several actions are still underway 3) and 4). Developing a highly detailed mapping of shared scientific resources—focusing on complementary, unique, and high-value infrastructure—is essential to position this shared infrastructure system as a unique tool for supporting high-level research. Additionally, ongoing discussions regarding access fees highlight the need to strike a balance between accessibility and sustainability. Ensuring the smooth integration of all partners, particularly those who have not yet finalized their participation, will require continued dialogue.

The project's success relies on extensive communication and proactive actions, such as Task 4.3's first call for projects, which will provide financial support for researchers aiming at use shared services or infrastructures. A methodological guide will further enhance this communication effort. These steps will improve accessibility and foster a strong scientific and technical identity within the alliance.

In conclusion, the UNITA initiative not only facilitates resource sharing but also embodies a broader vision of advancing scientific collaboration and excellence. By addressing existing challenges and maintaining its focus on inclusivity and innovation, the project has the potential to set a benchmark for inter-university partnerships across Europe, driving progress in education, research, and innovation.

Annexes

Annex 1: Task 4.3 initial program

Activities and division of work (WP description)					
Task No (continuous numbering linked to WP)	Task Name	Description	Participants		In-kind Contributions and Sub-contracting (Yes/No and which)
			Name	Role (COO, BEN, AE, AP, OTHER)	
T4.3	<p>UNITA sharing of infrastructures and Knowledge</p> <p>IND 4.3.a Number of infrastructures and related services in the interactive map</p> <p>Baseline 2022: 113</p> <p>Target 2027: 250</p> <p>Level: Alliance</p>	<p>Under this Task we will consolidate and implement the UNITA plan for sharing partners' infrastructures and related services, providing access to a range of users. We consider research infrastructures in the broad sense e.g., laboratory facilities, but also computing facilities and services. We will implement an Open Data policy in line with the 2016 European charter of access for research infrastructures and its principles and guidelines. The Task builds on the outcomes of the Re-UNITA project.</p> <p>This Task connects with Tasks 2.3 (Community), 4.2 (Research Hubs) and 3.4 (Digital campus).</p> <p>Task activities roadmap</p> <p>A4.3.1 Complete and update the mapping of partners infrastructures and related services developed by Re-UNITA (M1-M12): exchange of good practices regarding the management and sharing of infrastructures. Draw lessons for the further development and sharing of infrastructures and related serviced.</p> <p>A4.3.2 Consolidate the model for sharing research infrastructures and services, based on a decentralized management and Open Data approaches (M5-M15): agree on UNITA preferential fees, fee waivers and the allotment of costs. Prioritise access focusing on</p>	<p>UPPA</p> <p>UNITVB</p> <p>UNITO</p> <p>UBI</p> <p>IPG</p> <p>UNIZAR</p> <p>UPNA</p> <p>USMB</p> <p>UNIBS</p> <p>UVT</p> <p>HES-SO</p> <p>Orange, via Orange Romania</p> <p>ADITECH</p>	<p>BEN</p> <p>BEN</p> <p>COO</p> <p>BEN</p> <p>BEN</p> <p>BEN</p> <p>BEN</p> <p>BEN</p> <p>BEN</p> <p>BEN</p> <p>AP</p> <p>AP</p> <p>AP</p>	No

		<p>major and complementary infrastructures that have a greater potential of being used by all the partners (including Associated Partners and GEMINAE network) relevant to the alliance focus area in education and R&I aiming to become part of a European infrastructure project repository.</p> <p>A4.3.3 Launch regular calls to co-finance access to infrastructures (M13-M48) to enable researchers work, in priority on multi-partner projects, and also to address gaps in infrastructure, making proposals for longer-term solutions, involving national, private and EU funding. Set up an interactive user-friendly platform for infrastructure sharing in the UNITA inter-university digital campus to create a UNITA “scientific marketplace” and facilitate matchmaking partnerships, including training on infrastructures use. Implement and test the procedures for the systemic sharing of services and infrastructures and granting mutual access to facilities.</p> <p>A4.3.4 Assess the necessary system modifications (M13-M36) needed and the procedures being put in place to realise them at each partner institution and accommodate them legally, technically, and financially to develop a UNITA corporate identity of shared research services and infrastructures.</p> <p>A4.3.5 Enhance the system by adapting necessary changes and intensifying the sharing of services and infrastructures (M36-M48) to reach an integration of the areas of research capacities into the shared UNITA corporate identity. The widening process will integrate in the network the facilities provided by Associated Partners and GEMINAE partners.</p>			
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Annex 3: Infrastructures sharing agreement

Summary

<u>Abstract</u>	3
<u>1. Parties</u>	4
<u>2. Subject of the agreement</u>	4
<u>3. Duration and starting date of the action</u>	4
<u>4. Procedures</u>	5
<u>5. Modification of the agreement</u>	6
<u>6. Signatories of the agreement</u>	7

Abstract

1. Parties

This Agreement ("the Agreement") is between the following parties:

1. **UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO (UNITO)**, PIC 999861936, established in VIA GIUSEPPE VERDI 8, TORINO 10124, Italy,
2. **UNIVERSIDADE DA BEIRA INTERIOR (UBI)**, PIC 996437254, established in CONVENTO DE SANTO ANTONIO, COVILHA 6201 001, Portugal,
3. **UNIVERSITATEA TRANSILVANIA DIN BRASOV (UNITBV)**, PIC 999904131, established in BDUL EROILOR 29, BRASOV 500036, Romania,
4. **UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI BRESCIA (UNIBS)**, PIC 999893946, established in PIAZZA MERCATO 15, BRESCIA 25121, Italy,
5. **INSTITUTO POLITECNICO DA GUARDA (IPG)**, PIC 984924130, established in AV DR FRANCISCO DE SA CARNEIRO 50, GUARDA 6300 559, Portugal,
6. **UNIVERSIDAD PUBLICA DE NAVARRA (UPNA)**, PIC 999888029, established in CAMPUS DE ARROSADIA, PAMPLONA 31006, Spain,
7. **UNIVERSITE DE PAU ET DES PAYS DE L'ADOUR (UPPA)**, PIC 999849811, established in AVENUE DE L'UNIVERSITE, PAU 64000, France,
8. **UNIVERSITE SAVOIE MONT BLANC (USMB)**, PIC 999618078, established in RUE MARCOZ 27 DOMAINE UNIVERSITAIRE, CHAMBERY 73011, France,
9. **UNIVERSITATEA DE VEST DIN TIMISOARA (UVT)**, PIC 999635150, established in BD VASILE PARVAN 4, TIMISOARA 300223, Romania,
10. **UNIVERSIDAD DE ZARAGOZA (UNIZAR)**, PIC 999898214, established in CALLE PEDRO CERBUNA 12, ZARAGOZA 50009, Spain,

2. Subject of the agreement

The main objective is to establish the internal procedures for the creation of a network of shared research infrastructure and scientific datasets among UNITA's Higher Education Institutions, providing the researchers a database that includes these cutting-edge infrastructures from the different parties that can be used to improve their research through their use.

3. Duration and starting date of the action

The starting date of the action is 1st November 2023 and this Agreement will be valid till the end of the Unita project at 31st October 2027.

At the end of the project, this Agreement could be extended every year if all partners agree with it.

4. Procedures

We agree that the PROCEDURES for the use of shared research infrastructure and scientific datasets among UNITA's Higher Education Institutions are the following ones:

4.1 About the database

- The database consists in a file with relevant information about the available shared infrastructures and scientific datasets that will be presented to UNITA researchers through a specific web page.
- The structure of the database will be the one shown in the ANNEX I. New fields or categories may be included or deleted if all the partners agree to do so.
- Each Higher Education Institution is responsible for filling the database file with mandatory fields for each piece of equipment or service to be shared.
- The equipment will be shown in the database web page during the time that it is available to share. The minimum time for sharing is 6 months. Just in case of technical problems, this time can be reduced.
- Each Higher Education Institution can delete the equipment or scientific datasets from the database if needed informing the leader of WP4 - T4.3 at least 15 days before. Just in case of technical problems, this time can be reduced.
- UNIZAR will be the responsible for upgrading and maintaining the database, including hosting and maintenance. The database may be hosted in UNITA's web page in the future.

4.2 About the scientific resources to be shared between Higher Education Institutions

- Each partner will decide which pieces of equipment, laboratories or infrastructures, or scientific datasets (from now on 'equipment') will be added to the database.

UNITA - Agreement of UNITA's partners on the procedures to share scientific resources

- Each partner must assure the availability of the equipment while it is listed in the database.
- Each partner has to assure all the data protection measures applicable to the scientific datasets.
- Each equipment must have a responsible from the Higher Education Institutions that can be addressed by researchers to receive information about it.
- Each partner must assure that there is an internal procedure to share the equipment or the scientific datasets with partners from other Higher Education Institutions.

4.3 About the procedure to be followed by UNITA researchers

- The procedure to be followed by researchers that want to use shared equipment will be provided by each partner for its own equipment. In any case, each equipment included in the database must have a clear internal procedure to follow by any UNITA researcher that will be clearly indicated in the database and/or the webpage of the equipment or service and available in English.
- The use of the infrastructures and/or equipment by other UNITA's staff is subject to compliance with the health and safety rules established by the owner.
- The staff of any partner may have access to the other partner's premises, subject to compliance with the by-laws of the Higher Education Institutions controlling the premises and signing a specific hosting agreement if needed.
- The exchange of data (e.g., scientific datasets) performed in the scope of this agreement is confined to the signing entities of the alliance. The exchange of data should be performed securely. Datasets containing personal data (even when anonymized) should additionally be accompanied by the data protection impact assessment and further assurances of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance.

4.4 About on-site measurements

- If it is possible for the researchers to perform the measurements on-site it will be specifically indicated in the internal procedure.
- In the case that the equipment needs specialized technicians, the measurements will be made by them although the researcher can be present.
- In the case that the equipment can be used by the researchers, they will have to follow the internal procedures that may include to receive a course to use the equipment.
- Internal procedures may include a specific assurance to cover any problem with the use of the equipment.

4.5 About price

- There may be a price for the service that should cover the costs of operation of the equipment and, if stated by the owner's Higher Education Institutions, a specific assurance.
- It is expected that, as general rule (except if legal reasons avoid it), the price charged to other UNITA Higher Education Institutions will be the same that is employed for internal Works in each Higher Education Institution.
- The budget that each partner has from project UNITA (WP4 - T4.3) to perform this task will be used to maximize the number of exchanges. Particularly, partners are encouraged to finance the use of shared equipment by UNITA's cotutelle PhD students and for joint research projects.

4.6 About solution of possible problems

- The responsibility of each equipment is of the own Higher Education Institution so the possible problems that might arise will be solved within each Higher Education Institution following its internal rules.

4.7 About internal monitoring committee

- There will be an internal monitoring committee to this agreement. The monitoring committee will be formed by one member designed from each partner Higher Education Institution, the Unita Project Coordinator, the Unita Project Manager, and the leader of the Unita WP4 - T4.3. The monitoring committee will have to meet at least once every six months since the signing of the agreement to monitor its compliance.

5. Modification of the agreement

This agreement can be modified if necessary. If a partner wants to make any change it will be communicated to the leader of the T 4.3 (WP4) and discussed in the framework of the UNITA work package team. Any conflict will be solved by the Governance structures of UNITA.

6. Signatories of the agreement

1. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO (UNITO)

Signature

Name: Stefano Geuna

Title: Rector of Università Degli Studi Di Torino

Date: 29/01/2024

2. UNIVERSIDADE DA BEIRA INTERIOR (UBI)

Signature

UNITA - Agreement of UNITA's partners on the procedures to share scientific resources

Name: Mário Lino Barata Raposo

Title: Rector of Universidade Da Beira Interior

Date: 29/10/2024

3. UNIVERSITATEA TRANSILVANIA DIN BRASOV (UNITBV)

Signature

Name: Ioan Vasile Abrudan

Title: Rector of Universitatea Transilvania Din Brasov

Date: 29/10/24

4. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI BRESCIA (UNIBS)

Signature

Name: Francesco Castelli

Title: Rector of Universita Degli Studi Di Brescia

Date: 29/10/24

5. INSTITUTO POLITECNICO DA GUARDA (IPG)

Signature

Name: Joaquim Manuel Fernandes Brigas

Title: Rector of Instituto Politecnico Da Guarda

Date: 29-10-2024

6. UNIVERSIDAD PUBLICA DE NAVARRA (UPNA)

Signature

Name: Ramón Gonzalo García

Title: Rector of Universidad Publica De Navarra

Date: 29/10/24

7. UNIVERSITE DE PAU ET DES PAYS DE L'ADOUR (UPPA)

Signature

Name: Laurent Bordes

Title: Rector of Universite de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour

Date: 23/10/24

8. UNIVERSITE SAVOIE MONT BLANC (USMB)

Signature

Name: Philippe Galez

Title: Rector of Universite Savoie Mont Blanc

Date: 23/10/2024

9. UNIVERSITATEA DE VEST DIN TIMISOARA (UVT)

Signature

Name: Marilen Gabriel Pirtea

Title: Rector of Universitatea de Vest Din Timisoara

Date: 23.10.2024

UNITA - Agreement of UNITA's partners on the procedures to share scientific resources

10. UNIVERSIDAD DE ZARAGOZA (UNIZAR)

Signature

Name: José Mayoral Murillo

Title: Rector of Universidad De Zaragoza

Date: 20/10/2024